

A Study on the Draconian Prevalence of Alcoholism Leading To Domestic Violence: With Reference to Women Working In the Unorganized Sector of Thane District

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Abstract

In the era of women empowerment where the world is talking and witnessing growth and development of women in certain sections or sectors of the society, there is still a bleak disturbed subdued vulnerable picture which although known to the world at large is not been targeted for the simplest reason and understanding that it is ones private affair and not to be interfered with. This non interference policy of the State and society at large has many a times even killed God’s most beautiful creation called woman. There are eyes which cry blood, limbs broken by their very own, shattered souls working day and night for their families and these vulnerable lot having no one to complain to or probably no fruitful solution against this accepted violence faced at home by their very own. The root cause for this violence may be socially sanctified attitudes, male egos, societal acceptance legitimizing this irrational violent behavior or the culture in which we are brought up in and many a times the main culprit Alcohol. This Research paper is an attempt to bring to light the prevalence and ill- effects of Alcoholism leading to wife battering or domestic violence on the entire life

and living of women which not only leads to disturbed physical mental and emotional state of life but also manipulations and harassment outside home especially in the workplace with special reference to women working in the Unorganized or Informal Sector.

Key words: *Violence, Alcohol, Wife battering, domestic violence*

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INTRODUCTION

Violence at home especially under the influence of Alcoholic is an epidemic that kills, tortures physically and mentally and maims psychologically the most vulnerable target i.e woman. This woman could be anyone the mother, sister, daughter, daughter-in-law and definitely the wife. By whatever name addressed the plight is targeted towards one subdued goal that is the woman who is being taught right from childhood to accept silently all given to her in the name of love or relationship. This silent journey of a woman which starts right from when she is conceived to her death is accepted by herself, her very own and also the Society. Alcohol since times immemorial is known to corrupt minds thereby losing control over one's impulses, mind as well as anger. The effect of this Alcohol when it comes on a relationship is fully and wholly inflicted on the woman who bears it all silently. Many a times this poison of Alcohol is so strong that the man loses his job or is a source of problem to his family leading the family to further poverty. This vicious cycle of alcohol which on one side impairs the man of the house completely, leaving him financially and psychologically unsound and on the other hand the woman is battered, has to struggle

for food and basic necessities of life. Many a times due to the alcoholic habit of the husband leads to squandering of money or family pressure, poverty or even due to unemployment of husband a woman is forced to take up any employment mainly for fulfilling the dire needs of her family.

These family constraints can never be hidden at workplace and the exploitation there too starts which many a times does not get confined to long working hours with low wages but also sexual harassment at the hands of agents, supervisors or even employers. However the plight of woman is that the woman puts in more hours of work, cannot change her employment due to her illiteracy, unskilled nature of work and need of money and to add to the problem she is forced to do all household work bears up with all the battering in spite of sickness and undergoes immense mental and physical pain and agony. Her family too does not support her but she is criticized for working long hours yet getting low wages, her character is many times questioned and all these have a circular flow in a woman's life without any end. She is manipulated and exploited at her workplace as well as at home.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the prevalence of Alcoholism and wife battering in the Society
- To identify the problems related to Alcoholism and its ill-effects on the family.
- To study the link between Alcoholism and Wife battering or Domestic Violence
- To study the problems and exploitation faced by women within and outside home especially those working in the Unorganized Sector.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Rebello (1982) elaborated on domestic violence stating and attributing the reasons for domestic violence to be right from husbands drunkenness to conflict over household expenses or superiority over decision making, extra marital affairs etc.

Shubakumar et al. (2005) concluded that among 9938 subjects, 40% of Indian women have experienced some sort of spousal violence leading to deterioration in mental health.

Audinarayana (2011) reported that partners' frequency of alcohol consumption and the father ever beat mother are the most significant factors influencing physical and emotional violence.

Varshney Shweta (2011) in her paper talks on how Rural women share extreme abundant responsibilities and perform multiple roles running the families, working on farms and inspite of all the hard work they are not paid well in terms of wages, exploited, manipulated at home and outside and their work is considered socially secondary and goes unnoticed.

Dr. A.B.Siddiqui (2013) in “**Domestic Violence on Women in India**” evaluates domestic violence its nature and types within the boundaries of home where the woman comes with dreams of a happy married life. The Author has used the word Intimate Terrorism to cover issues of couple violence along with Sexual Abuse. The Author has cited the Cycle of Abuse from one ranging from the Tension building phase to acute battering episode and the Honeymoon phase. The Author has also covered violence on children and old women within their homes by their very near and dear ones.

METHODOLOGY

The **Secondary** sources included Reports of various commissions and committees, Books, Research papers and review reports published in journals and newspaper As **Primary** source the research study was mainly based on data collected through field interviews. The tools used for primary data collection were structured interviews cum Schedules and on-field observations. In order to get an insight and deeper knowledge of the research issue a Field Research through Survey that is Schedule was conducted for more than 8 months in the different areas or regions of Thane District. Women engaged in allied work or occupations in the unorganized or informal sector such namely construction workers, agricultural workers, fisher women, beauticians, domestic maids, vegetable vendors, rag pickers, aayabai's, tailors and papad making workers a total of 150 of them were interviewed through a structured questionnaire. These workers were surveyed or interviewed to find different problems and aspects of their profession and family life hence the questionnaire covered important characteristics such as their personal profile, socio economic background, alcoholism of their husbands, earning capacity of their husbands, need for entry in work, problems faced, Violence

faced at home such as wife battering, etc. Violence of all types especially Domestic Violence being a sensitive issue the women were assured confidentiality and anonymity. To simplify the large quantities of numerical data the following statistical techniques with the help of SPSS version 20 were used namely

- ❖ Logistic Regression Analysis
- ❖ Chi-Square Test

FINDINGS THROUGH SURVEY

TABLE 1 : Battering by Husband

Status	Frequency	Percent
Yes	114	76
No	27	18
No Response & N.A	9	6
Total	150	100

The above table alarmingly depicts that battering by husband was rampant. Total 114 Respondents reported husband battering and only 27 reported negatively against it. There were 9 who were either not married or divorced and estranged who did not report or gave a no response. It is a shocking truth that

✚ inspite of legislations and laws wife battering is still rampantly practiced in the name of correction of wife or satisfaction of male ego or otherwise.

✚ Inspite of Domestic Violence Act, 2005 the rate of wife battering has not reduced which only calls for effective and strict implementation of the same provided it is reported to the police.

Figure 1

In spite of the different great epics elevating the position of women into that of goddess, the reality still remains that they are mercilessly battered by their very own or we can say the by the ones who once upon a time took the oath to take care of their wives batter them according to their whims and

fancies to remind them of their subordinate positions and get easy sanction by the society. Most of the times, it is seen that even the other family members do not object to such battering thinking it to be a private affair.

Table 2 : Alcoholic Husband

Status	Frequency	Percent
Yes	101	67.3
No	43	28.7
No Response	6	4.0
Total	150	100.0

Figure 2

The above table shows that out of 150 Women Respondents interviewed, 101 said that their husbands were into the alcoholic habit which has led to their distressed state of life and living. Among the 6 who gave no Response were either widows or not married or estranged. It was surprising even to hear

the widow and the estranged saying that it is pointless and bad to talk of people who have left them forever. This shows the culture in which women are brought up to let go and forgive their very own ones even if they were the worst.

Table 3 : During the drunkenness

Status	Frequency	Percent
Yes	83	55.3
No	40	26.7
No Response	27	18.0
Total	150	100.0

Figure 3

The above table depicts the status of the husband in terms of his alcoholic behavior causing further violence. Out of 101 Respondents reported that their husbands were alcoholic the main problem of their lives (Table 2), 83 of the women agreed that maximum battering took place during the state of drunkenness. 40 were also of the

opinion that the battering was common irrespective of the husband drunk or not and 27 preferred to be silent about their husbands state of drunkenness and it leading to violence at home. 83 women strongly agreed that if alcohol be removed from their husbands so called diet it would definitely reduce violence at home.

Table 4 : Opinion about accepting violence in life

Status	Frequency	Percent
Yes	123	82.0
No	27	18.0
Total	150	100.0

Figure 4

The above table depicts that 123 of the women respondents felt that violence was a part of their lives and it was an inescapable silent journey. Majority of them had witnessed violence at some time or the other and were most of the time silent about it. The mindset about going to police or making private violence public and making a mockery of oneself was deeply imbibed in them. Their trust and confidence on law and the laws enforcement machinery was bleak and hence they preferred to accept violence rather than complain about the same.

In most cases especially of reported cases of women working in the construction industry as well as who work as rag pickers face a common problem more of the agent rather than the main employer. They fear the loss

of job if they are unable to keep them happy and so most cases are ignored or accepted. Many women also have reported that the loss of job would bring their family to a standstill as they are the main source of bread earners. Many women also know their status quo that they are illiterate as well as unskilled and if they protest any such favors asked for they would be out of jobs and getting a new job is still more an issue. Similarly there is no guarantee that the new job or new agent or employer will not repeat the same. Many of the women did not file a complaint or leave the workplace where they faced sexual harassment for the simplest of reasons that they would have to confront their husbands with reasons of leaving the work and were very sure that their character would be in question and a new form of

repeated violence would start at home. So it would be best on their part to gain some monetary reliefs rather than face battering at home.

Sad but the truth of most of their lives that these women working in the Unorganized or Informal Sector face severe battering at home for no fault, have to go out for work each day with a new challenge and face exploitation and manipulation there too. They very well know that they cannot afford to complain to anyone at home not even their better half as the family and most importantly their husband who should be their backbone to survive would again harass and batter them for not getting money for their luxury or may be drunkenness. Alcoholism leading to wife battering is getting bad to worse each day and even though India has beautifully drafted laws the implementation is lacking and moreover the change- over of mindset is lacking which is the root cause of all agony at home leading to distress outside.

Perpetuating and demonstrating the historically unequal powers, gender discrimination impedes the full and wholesome growth and progress of all in the society young and old irrespective of gender and class and impedes the growth of future

too as the seeds sown itself reflect and bring about negativism and stagnation. In the process the growth of the entire society is shunned and stunted.

It needs to be understood very clearly that the price of violence paid by a woman is not only monetary. Violence of all and any types small and big cause an inestimable cost of lost productivity by individuals who are damaged physically, emotionally, mentally, psychologically as well as economically. It is the stories of women who face domestic violence almost every day yet live with the same man for a variety of reasons still hoping that one day things will change and her dream too like a normal human will come true.

Even in cases of Domestic Violence it must be publically acknowledged as a problem. Children and Women and children must be helped so as to stop violence and the issues related to teachings right from childhood that for every wrong a woman is to held liable and accountable needs a mental change. Similarly remaining silent, excusing violence, blaming themselves overall issues and accepting cultural rationales blindly should be stopped by awareness programs.

CONCLUSION

The root cause of many evils Alcohol needs to be looked into with lot of care and hence the Government should make an attempt to ban all centers or shops of alcohol. The Alcoholics should be counseled as well as the shop owners should be provided with alternate employment or subsidiaries. Even though closing down of such shops will cause a great toll to the revenue generation of the Government and sound impractical it is the only resort which some day or the other has to be implemented for the benefit of thousands or even more of women who are targeted each and every day with this dreadful evil.

May be this suggestion would sound very unrealistic but some attempt on the part of the Government or some tie-up of Government with NGO's would help to change if not completely alter the situation in India. May be also when women too get up and stand for their rights united and courageously can the situation at home and workplace be improved. May be for this changed situation education and economic independence would be required. It is again a cycle of growth and empowerment against the cycle of alcoholism and wife battering. In the long run only we women can bring change for ourselves.

The Community and society is largely to be blamed for these and many more types or kinds of violence which are prevalent in the society in the guise of customs and rituals. The time has come when the society should learn to address these wrong doers stringently so that can be the new practice for the new generation to come.

The family and the Society should come together with definitely the women at the forefront and address these issues urgently and without prejudices and biases. It is only when the attitude, values and ideologies change that woman can get justice. Only when the society as a whole acknowledges the role of woman in a man's life and the society that violence any where can be curbed. This emancipation can never be a one day story but it is never late to begin with.

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